

(Awareness and Utilization of Artificial Intelligence tools for STEM Teaching among ... Muhammad, A. S., Et. al., 2025)

Awareness and Utilization of Artificial Intelligence tools for STEM Teaching among Secondary School Teachers in Sabon-Gari, Kaduna State, Nigeria

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Abstract

The integration of AI in education has gained global recognition for its potential to enhance teaching effectiveness and improve learning outcomes. This study examined the awareness and utilization of Artificial Intelligence (AI) tools among secondary school STEM teachers in Sabon-Gari Local Government Area, Kaduna State, Nigeria. A descriptive survey design was adopted for the study involving a sample size of 160 randomly selected STEM teachers from public secondary schools during the 2023/2024 academic session. Data were collected using a validated instrument titled Teachers Awareness and Utilization of Artificial Intelligence Questionnaire (TAUAIQ) with reliability coefficient 0.76 which was calculated using Cronbach alpha. Research questions were answered using frequencies, percentages, mean and standard deviation while null hypotheses were tested using PPMC and Chi-square. Results revealed moderate awareness (48.7%) and utilization (49.5%) of AI tools, with teachers more aware of Socratic by Google, Mathway, and Google AI Experiments, while advanced AI tools such as Cognii and Quillionz were less known and utilized. Key challenges identified included inadequate training, high costs, poor internet connectivity, lack of administrative support, and limited instructional time. A significant relationship was found between AI awareness and utilization ($p < .05$), while no significant relationship existed between the challenges faced and AI tool utilization ($p > .05$). The study concluded that although AI awareness and utilization are increasing, integration remains limited due to systemic and infrastructural barriers. It recommends targeted capacity-building, improved digital infrastructure, administrative policy support, and AI integration into the STEM curriculum to enhance effective adoption in Nigerian secondary schools.

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Keywords: Artificial Intelligence, STEM education, AI Awareness, AI Utilization

Introduction: Education in the fields of science, technology, engineering, and mathematics (STEM) is essential to any country's progress. In every facet of human endeavor, research and development have accelerated the development and invention of various advancements through science and technology (Fasola, 2024). In the rapidly changing field of education, artificial intelligence (AI) has become an innovative force that provides creative answers to enduring problems (Ujunwa et al., 2025). Artificial intelligence (AI) is rapidly transforming STEM education by offering fresh and inventive approaches to enhancing STEM instruction at all education levels. This makes it possible for STEM educators to adapt to the rapid technological advancements of the twenty-first century. Tools for Artificial Intelligence (AI) are being incorporated into the teaching and learning process, opening up new avenues for raising educational standards. These tools can help teachers manage different classroom situations, provide individualized learning experiences, and enable real-time assessment. Sajja et al. (2024) defined Artificial Intelligence (AI) in education as the application of state-of-the-art technologies to support educational processes, such as automated grading, personalized learning, and intelligent tutoring systems. According to Ujunwa et al. (2025), by addressing particular demands such as customized lesson plans, adaptable learning environments, and effective administrative support, the use of AI in education may significantly improve teaching effectiveness.

In recent years, the application of AI to science education has grown in prominence worldwide. According to research, using AI-powered tools like interactive simulations, adaptive learning platforms, and customized feedback systems can significantly increase student engagement, knowledge retention, and critical thinking (UNESCO, 2021). In Nigeria, more individuals have noticed the potential of AI in education. The 2020 National Policy on Education places a strong emphasis on how incorporating technology into the classroom can improve quality, equity, and access. Additionally, Oliveira et al. (2019) reviewed the literature on emergent technologies from the scientific education field. The study demonstrated how learners' experiences are being enhanced by emergent technology artifacts like computer simulations, virtual labs, mobile devices, and robotics. Thus, this study demonstrates that new technologies have opened up a plethora of opportunities for instructors to advance. Through the utilization of AI in education, teachers may focus on building relationships with students, getting to know them, and developing abilities that will help them on their path to human growth instead of having to perform certain repetitive duties (Ikedinachi et al., 2019).

A study by Glory et al. (2024) demonstrated how AI has been incorporated into education through the use of learning platforms, web browsers, smart devices, intelligent books, and tutoring systems. Through the use of AI, students can explore pertinent learning materials, manage their learning activities, and receive authentic, pertinent information. This makes them curious learners rather than passive recipients of information and knowledge from lecturers alone. Increasing self-learning and active engagement in the learning process as a result.

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Teachers are in the forefront of implementing innovative teaching strategies in schools to engage students and improve learning results, claim Pacheco-Mendoza et al. (2023). According to research by Krichen and Abdalzaher (2024), AI systems get better with time thanks to experience or new data, and they frequently complete tasks with greater accuracy. According to Fasola (2024), the use of AI-based technologies, such as personalized learning platforms, intelligent tutoring systems, and automated grading, could fundamentally alter the way educators teach. However, how well these AI tools are embraced and utilized will depend on how well-informed and knowledgeable the educators are.

The potential of AI for science education has been the subject of an increasing amount of research in recent years. Several research have shown how well AI-based interventions can enhance students' learning results in a range of science courses (Okoye et al., 2023). Al Darayseh (2023) in his study on the application of AI in science education reported progress in the use of AI in teaching and learning. In their study, Huang and Qiao (2024) discovered that the incorporation of Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics (STEM) education in AI training improved the experimental group of students' computational thinking skills, learning motivation, and self-efficacy. Thus, studies above establish the fact that the application of AI in science education has a substantial influence and presents a number of prospects. Ibrahim et al. (2024) also stated that schools may support the prevention of AI abuse and guarantee that it functions as a useful tool rather than a distraction by defining rules for how teachers and students should engage with it. Generative AI has been demonstrated to help solve issues and clarify difficult ideas in STEM education, particularly in the areas of science and mathematics.

The use of AI in secondary schools in Nigeria is not without challenges, though. Okonkwo and Nwankwo (2022) outlined important obstacles to the use of AI, such as inadequate resources, a lack of training for teachers in AI technologies, and worries about data privacy and the moral application of AI in the classroom. This underlined the necessity for focused investments in digital infrastructure and extensive professional development programs to prepare educators for the integration of AI tools in their teaching practices. Although many educators were aware of the promise of AI technology, Adelana and Akinyemi (2021) discovered that their knowledge of generative AI was rather inadequate. This results from a lack of training and digital tools. According to Onuh (2024), there are concerns regarding how AI tools affect teachers teaching practices as a result of the growing use of technology in the classroom. Although AI holds great potential for enhanced accessibility to resources and individualized learning, little empirical study has been done on how it affects secondary school. Additionally, there are differences in how teachers view AI tools, which might impact students' academic achievement and lead to differences in the effectiveness of teaching. Investigating secondary school teachers' knowledge of and use of AI in STEM education in Sabon Gari Local Government Area, Kaduna state, Nigeria, is therefore necessary. Therefore, the present study investigates the awareness and utilization of AI

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tools among secondary school teachers for teaching STEM subjects in Sabon-Gari Local Government Area of Kaduna State, Nigeria.

Statement of the Research Problem: The integration of Artificial Intelligence (AI) tools in education has attracted growing interest in recent years, especially regarding their potential to enhance teaching effectiveness. Despite the proliferation of digital technologies, many schools still rely heavily on outdated instructional methods (Akpan, 2024). This continued dependence on traditional teaching approaches highlights a critical gap in the adoption of innovative tools. Onuh (2024) attributes this reliance to a lack of adequate training and institutional support, which hinders teachers from effectively incorporating AI tools into their instructional practices, resulting in inconsistent and limited use of these technologies. Furthermore, the successful integration of AI in education necessitates more than just having access to tools; it also requires pedagogical and content knowledge that is tailored to digital environments (Akpan, 2024). Mutahir and Falade (2024) point out that AI-enabled teaching has the potential to significantly improve students' engagement and performance, especially in science disciplines, through intelligent tutoring, adaptive learning systems, and personalized learning pathways. Therefore, the present study investigates the awareness and utilization of AI tools among secondary school teachers for teaching STEM subjects in Sabon-Gari Local Government Area of Kaduna State, Nigeria.

Objectives of the study: The purpose of this study was to investigate secondary school teachers Awareness and Utilization of Artificial Intelligence in teaching STEM in Sabon-Gari Local Government Area of Kaduna State, Nigeria. Specifically, the study:

- i. Investigated teachers' awareness of AI for teaching STEM in secondary schools
- ii. Found out teachers' utilization of AI tools for teaching STEM in secondary schools
- iii. Ascertained the challenges facing the use of Artificial intelligence for teaching STEM in secondary schools.

Research Questions: The following research questions were raised and answered:

- i. What is the level of teachers' awareness of AI for teaching STEM in secondary schools in Sabon-Gari Local Government Area of Kaduna State, Nigeria?
- ii. What is the level teachers' utilization of AI tools for teaching STEM in secondary schools?
- iii. What are the challenges faced by teachers in use of AI tools for teaching in STEM in secondary schools?

Hypotheses: The following null hypotheses were formulated and tested at 0.05 level of significance:

H₀₁: There is no significant relationship in the level of teachers' awareness and utilization of AI tools for teaching STEM in secondary schools in Sabon Gari LGA, Kaduna State, Nigeria.

H₀₂: There is no significant relationship between the challenges faced by teachers and their use of AI tools for teaching STEM in secondary schools.

Methodology

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The study adopted descriptive research of the survey type. The population for this study comprised all STEM secondary school teachers during the 2023/2024 academic session in Sabon-Gari local government area of Kaduna State, Nigeria. One hundred and sixty (160) teachers were selected using random sampling technique from all the public secondary schools Sabon-Gari Local Government Area, Kaduna state, Nigeria.

Data for the study were collected using a structured questionnaire titled "Teachers Awareness and Utilization of Artificial Intelligence Questionnaire (TAUIQ). The questionnaire consisted of 30 items and was divided into two sections. Section A gathered demographic information about the respondents, while Section B addressed the research questions, divided into two. Section 'A' assessed teachers' awareness of AI tools for STEM teaching, with responses rated on a two-point scale: "Aware" (A) and "Not Aware" (NA). Section 'B' focused on teachers' utilization of AI tools, also using a two-point scale: "Utilized" (U) and "Not Utilized" (NU) while Section 'C' assessed the challenges faced by STEM teachers in using AI using 5-point Likert scale of Strongly Agree (SA), Agree (A), Disagree (D), and Strongly Disagree (SD). The instrument was validated by two experts from the Department of Psychology and Counselling, Ahmadu Bello University Zaria, Kaduna State, Nigeria. The reliability coefficient for the instrument was found to be 0.76, indicating a high level of reliability. Data collected were analyzed using frequencies, percentages, means, standard deviations, PPMC and Chi-square.

Presentation of Results

These consist of descriptive statistics used to answer research questions; appropriate statistics used for testing hypothesis; Tables should be aligned to APA style; P-value compare with decision threshold – 0.05 significance if necessary.

Research Question One: What is the level of teachers' awareness of AI for teaching STEM in secondary schools in Sabon-Gari Local Government Area of Kaduna State, Nigeria?

Table 1: Percentage of Teachers' Awareness of AI for Teaching STEM in Secondary Schools in Sabon-Gari Local Government Area of Kaduna State, Nigeria.

S/N	Tools	Aware (%)	Not Aware (%)
1.	Labster	48.7	51.2
2.	Socratic by Google	54.3	45.6
3.	Quillionz	44.3	55.6
4.	Cognii	50.0	50.0
5.	Carnegie Learning	47.5	52.5
6.	Century Tech	47.5	52.5
7.	Mathway	42.5	57.5
8.	Edmentum Exact Path	46.8	53.1
9.	Jupyter Notebook	47.5	52.5
10.	Google AI Experiments	58.7	41.2
	Percentage (%)	(48.7%)	(51.7%)

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Table 1 indicates the level of teachers’ awareness of AI for teaching STEM in secondary schools of Sabon-Gari Local Government Area, Kaduna state, Nigeria. The table further revealed that, 48.7% of the sampled secondary school teachers indicated that they are aware of AI in teaching STEM, while 51.7% indicated that they are not aware of AI in teaching STEM.

Research Question Two: What is the level of teachers’ utilization of AI tools for teaching STEM in secondary schools?

Table 2: Percentage of Teachers’ Utilization of AI for Teaching STEM in Secondary Schools in Sabon-Gari Local Government Area of Kaduna State, Nigeria.

S/N	Tools	Utilize (%)	Not Utilize (%)
1.	Labster	47.5	52.5
2.	Socratic by Google	50.6	49.3
3.	Quillionz	41.8	58.1
4.	Cognii	46.2	53.7
5.	Carnegie Learning	49.3	50.6
6.	Century Tech	53.7	46.2
7.	Mathway	52.5	47.5
8.	Edmentum Exact Path	56.8	43.1
9.	Jupyter Notebook	45.0	55.0
10.	Google AI Experiments	51.8	48.1
	Percentage (%)	(49.5%)	(50.4%)

Table 2 indicates the level of teachers’ utilization of AI for teaching STEM in secondary schools of Sabon-Gari Local Government Area, Kaduna state, Nigeria. The table further revealed that, 49.5% of the sampled secondary school teachers indicated that they are aware of AI in teaching STEM, while 50.4% indicated that they are not aware of AI in teaching STEM.

Research Question Three: What are the challenges faced by teachers in use of AI tools for teaching in STEM in secondary schools?

Table 3: Mean and Standard Deviation of the Challenges faced by Teachers in use of AI Tools for Teaching STEM.

S/N	Statement	Mean	Standard
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			Deviation
1.	Lack of adequate training on how to use AI tools	2.97	1.42
2.	Insufficient access to AI tools and digital resources in schools	2.93	1.40
3.	High cost of acquiring and maintaining AI-supported tools and platforms	3.01	1.30
4.	Poor internet connectivity affects the effective use of AI tools in teaching STEM subjects	2.98	1.33
5.	Lack of administrative support for integrating AI tools in the classroom	3.10	1.48
6.	Limited time within the school timetable to use AI tools effectively	2.91	1.41
7.	Fear of technology replacing the role of teachers	3.03	1.42
Grand Mean (X)		2.99	1.39

Table 3 indicates the challenges faced by teachers in the use of AI for teaching STEM. The mean score of all the items is above the benchmark of 2.45. Lack of administrative support for integrating AI tools in the classroom had the highest mean score of 3.10 with a standard deviation of 1.48 while limited time within the school timetable to use AI tools effectively had the lowest mean score of 2.91 and a standard deviation of 1.41 respectively.

Testing Null Hypotheses

Null Hypothesis One: There is no significant relationship between awareness of AI tools and utilization of AI tools for teaching by STEM secondary school teachers in Sabon gari LGA, Kaduna state, Nigeria.

Table 4: Chi-square test Statistics on the Relationship between Awareness of AI tools and Utilization of AI tools for Teaching by STEM Secondary School Teachers in Sabon Gari LGA, Kaduna state, Nigeria.

Variables	Df	Alpha(α)	X²_{cal}	X²_{tab}	p-value	Decision
Awareness of AI tools and utilization of AI tools	16	0.05	153.13	26.29	0.000	H ₀ rejected

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Level of significance $\alpha < 0.05$ significant Level

Table 4 shows the Chi-square statistics (χ^2) on the relationship between awareness of AI tools and utilization of AI tools for teaching by STEM secondary school teachers in Sabon gari LGA, Kaduna state, Nigeria. The calculated Chi-square value ($X^{cal}=153.13$) was greater than the tabulated Chi-square value ($X^{tab}=26.29$) at 0.05 level of significance. Therefore, the null hypothesis which states that, there is no significant relationship between awareness of AI tools and utilization of AI tools for teaching by STEM secondary school teachers in Sabon gari LGA, Kaduna state, Nigeria was hereby rejected.

Null Hypothesis Two: There is no significant relationship between the challenges faced by teachers and their use of AI tools for teaching STEM in secondary schools.

Table 5: Relationship Between the Challenges Faced by Teachers and Their Use of AI Tools for Teaching STEM in Secondary Schools in Sabon Gari LGA, Kaduna State, Nigeria

Correlations

		Challenges Faced		Use_of_AI_Tools
Spearman's rho	Challenges_Faced	Correlation Coefficient	1.000	-.040
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.	.611
		N	160	160
Use_of_AI_Tools	Use_of_AI_Tools	Correlation Coefficient	-.040	1.000
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.611	.
		N	160	160

Table 5 shows the result of a Spearman Rank- Order Correlation to examine the relationship between the challenges faced by teachers and their use of AI tools for teaching STEM in secondary schools. The result showed no significant relationship between the two variables, the p-value calculated 0.611 is greater than the alpha value of 0.05. This implies that, there is no statistically significant relationship between the challenges faced by teachers and their use of AI tools in teaching STEM subjects. Hence, the null hypothesis which states that, there is no significant relationship between the challenges faced by teachers and their use of AI tools for teaching STEM in secondary schools was hereby retained.

Discussion of Findings

Findings on the level of teachers' awareness of AI tools revealed that teachers were more aware of AI tools such as Mathway, Socratic by Google, and Google AI Experiments, while awareness of AI tools like Cognii, Quillionz, Carnegie Learning, and Century Tech was considerably lower. This finding is in agreement with that of Olokooba et al (2024) and Fasola (2024) who reported that, teachers are aware of AI tools. The findings are also in line with that of Thomas et al (2024) who found that, lecturers were aware of AI for education irrespective of their academic qualifications

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in a Nigerian university. However, the finding is in disagreement with the studies of Aldosari (2020) and Alkanaana (2022) who revealed that, there is a low level of pre-service science teachers' awareness of employing AI in science education, with a significant decrease in awareness of how to utilize AI in science education.

Findings of the study further revealed that STEM teachers in Sabon-Gari LGA face several challenges in integrating AI tools into their teaching practices. Challenges include; high cost of acquiring and maintaining AI-supported tools and platforms, lack of adequate training on how to use AI tools, high cost of acquiring and maintaining AI-supported tools and platforms, poor internet connectivity affects the effective use of AI tools in teaching STEM subjects, lack of administrative support for integrating AI tools in the classroom, limited time within the school timetable to use AI tools effectively and fear of technology replacing the role of teachers. These challenges hinder the effective utilization of AI tools by STEM teachers and suggest the need for targeted interventions to address these barriers. This finding confirms with that of Kwara Learn (2023) and Olokooba (2024) who identified high internet costs and limited training as significant barriers to AI adoption in schools.

Conclusion

Based on the findings of this study, it can be concluded that although there is an increasing level of awareness and moderate utilization of AI tools in teaching STEM subjects, the utilization is still largely limited to a few commonly known and accessible tools. Teachers' engagement with more advanced or specialized AI educational platforms remains low. The study further concludes that effective integration of AI tools in STEM education is hindered by several challenges, including Lack of administrative support, fear of technology replacing teachers' role, among others. Unless these challenges are addressed, the full potential of AI in enhancing STEM teaching and learning within secondary schools in Sabon-Gari-Local Government Area, Kaduna state, Nigeria may not be realized.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations are made:

- i. Education authorities, school administrators, and teacher training institutions should organize regular workshops, seminars, and capacity-building programs to enhance teachers' skills in the effective use of AI tools for STEM education.
- ii. Government and private stakeholders should invest in providing schools with up-to-date digital infrastructures, AI-supported educational tools, and reliable internet services to promote AI integration in STEM classrooms.
- iii. School management and administrators should provide strong leadership support by including AI integration initiatives in school policies and budget allocations, and by creating incentives for AI adoption in STEM classrooms.

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- iv. Curriculum planners should integrate AI-based tools, simulations, and virtual learning activities into the STEM curriculum to enhance regular usage and skills development among teachers and students.

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